

g/litre did not control *L. natalensis*. Metaldehyde inefficiency at the highest concentration and efficiency at lower concentrations may have been due to a protective mechanism developed by

Limnea. B. aegyptiaca nut and leaf powder controlled *L. natalensis*, but concentrations higher than 0.75 g leaf powder/litre harmed azolla. *D. heudelotianum* affected neither

Limnea nor azolla. Treating azolla multiplication plots with 0.25 g *D. heudelotianum* bark powder or *B. aegyptiaca* leaf powder provides an effective, inexpensive control. \mathcal{L}

Nitrogen use efficiency in rice

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We evaluated urea split, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), neem-coated urea (NCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), urea supergranules (USG), and urea coal acid (UCA) with 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha for rice at Varanasi. The experiment was in a split-plot design with N sources in main plots and levels in subplots.

Four doses of the coated fertilizers and USG were applied 1 wk after transplanting Jaya. Half of urea split was basal and half in equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. PK at 22-42 kg/ha were applied at transplanting. Fields were flooded with 5±2 cm water throughout the study.

USG performed best, followed by SCU and NCU (see table). Each N increment significantly increased grain yield. \mathcal{L}

Effect of N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1982	1983
N sources		
Urea split	3.1	3.0
SCU	3.5	3.2
NCU	3.2	3.2
LCU	2.8	3.1
GCU	3.2	3.0
USG	3.5	3.2
UCA	2.5	3.0
S. Em ±	0.1	0.08
LSD 5%	0.4	0.2
N levels (kg/ha)		
0	2.2	1.9
40	3.0	2.8
80	3.4	3.6
120	3.9	4.1
S. Em ±	0.1	0.06
LSD 5%	0.4	0.2

Effect of sowing time on yield of rice varieties in two locations in Cuba

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Even slight changes in sowing time will substantially change yield and duration of rice varieties. In 1977-80 we recorded the effect of year-around sowing on modern rices.

Varietal response and interaction between variety and sowing date was highly significant in all 36 sowings. Dry season (Nov-Mar) grain yield averaged

1.5 t/ha more than that in wet season (Apr-Oct), independent of variety.

Medium-duration IR880-C9, Caribe-1, and IR1529 performed best when planted from December to August (see figure), depending upon location. Short-duration P723 yielded better when planted from late December to March, and from April to early August. Photoperiod-sensitive Caribe-7 should be planted from April to June.

Because of low temperature during reproductive stage, September to November sowings generally yielded lowest. \mathcal{L}

Favorable sowing range for 5 rices in Cuba.

Seasonal variation in azolla biomass production in Jorhat

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Azolla pinnata grows naturally in low-lying fields, shallow ditches, and channels in Assam. In 1981-82 we

studied azolla biomass production with different levels of inoculants and nutrients (see table) in 4-m² dugout plots lined with 750 gauge black polythene. The experiment had three replications.

Seasonal azolla growth varied significantly. Azolla biomass production increased from Mar to Jun, declined in